

Hydrolysis of Chloro-, Ethoxy- and Methoxy-2-cyano-4-nitrobenzenes.

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The methods commonly employed for the hydrolysis of substituted aromatic nitriles may be classified as follows:—

(a) Hydrolysis by boiling with dilute sulphuric acid; Claus and Kurz (*J. pr. Chem.*, 1888, ii, 37, 196) have by this method hydrolysed *p*-chloro-*m*-nitro-, *p*-chloro-*o*-nitro- and *m*-chloro-*o*-nitrobenzonitriles into the corresponding acids. In many cases, however, action proceeds no farther than the formation of the acid amide (*vide* Küster and Stallberg, *Annalen*, 1894, 278, 207, regarding hydrolysis of nitro- β -isoduronitrile).

(b) Hydrolysis by heating with concentrated hydrochloric acid under pressure; Küster and Stallberg (*loc. cit.*) have thus hydrolysed nitro- and dinitro- β -isoduronitrile by heating with concentrated hydrochloric acid in sealed tubes at about 200°.

(c) Digestion of the nitrile with 85 or 90% sulphuric acid at 100° (*cf.* Bouveault, *Bull. Soc. chim.*, 1892, iii, 9, 368), when the amide is formed, the conversion into acid being effected by dissolving the amide in cold strong sulphuric acid and adding the requisite amount of cold concentrated sodium nitrite at 30°, finally warming for a few moments to 40-50°. Sudborough's method (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1895, 67, 601) is a modification of Bouveault and consists in heating the nitrile with a large excess of 90% sulphuric acid for 1 hour at 120-3°, adding to the well cooled solution the theoretical amount of sodium nitrate and warming on the water-bath until effervescence ceases.

(d) The method of Berger and Olivier (*Rec. trav. Chim.*, 1927, 46, 600) who find that 2:6-dimethylbenzonitrile, which is not hydrolysed by 90% sulphuric acid or even by methyl or amyl alcoholic potash, is hydrolysed by concentrated sulphuric acid merely to 2:6-dimethylbenzamide, this amide being hydrolysed into the acid only by 100% phosphoric acid at 145-50°.

The method found most convenient by the authors for the hydrolysis of 1-chloro-, 1-ethoxy- and 1-methoxy-2-cyano-4-nitrobenzenes is described in the experimental section.

1-Chloro-2-cyano-4-nitrobenzene is hydrolysed by sulphuric acid first into 2-chloro-5-nitrobenzamide and the latter, on boiling with hydrochloric acid, yields 2-chloro-5-nitrobenzoic acid. The nitrile, the amide and the acid, on boiling with aqueous or alcoholic potash, yield 5-nitrosalicylic acid, a conversion which has also been noticed in the case of the acid by Purgotti and Contardi (*Gazzetta*, 1902, *i* 32, 526).

Ethoxy- and methoxy-2-cyano-4-nitrobenzenes are similarly hydrolysed by sulphuric acid into 2-ethoxy-5-nitrobenzamide and 2-methoxy-5-nitrobenzamide respectively. They are hydrolysed by hydrochloric acid respectively into 2-ethoxy-5-nitrobenzoic acid previously made by Perkin (*Annalen*, 1868, 145, 312) by nitration of *o*-ethoxybenzaldehyde, and by Kraut (*Annalen*, 1869, 150, 4) by nitration of *o*-ethoxybenzoic acid and 2-methoxy-5-nitrobenzoic acid previously made by Kraut (*loc. cit.*) and Salkowski (*Annalen*, 1874, 173, 41) by nitration of *o*-methoxybenzoic acid, and by Hale and Robertson (*Amer. Chem. J.* 1908, 39, 688) by permanganate oxidation of 2-acetyl-4-nitrophenol-methylether. The ethoxy- and methoxynitrobenzotriles, the amides and the acids are all converted by caustic potash into 5-nitrosalicylic acid.

The series of observations mentioned above may be conveniently represented by the scheme shown in the next page.

It would not be out of place to mention here that whereas 1-chloro-2-cyano-4-nitrobenzene is hydrolysed by strong sulphuric acid or hydrochloric acid or caustic potash, none of these agents is able to hydrolyse 1-chloro-2-cyano-4-aminobenzene obtained by the reduction of 1-chloro-2-cyano-4-nitrobenzene. This interesting observation seems to show how the substitution of the nitro group in chloro-2-cyano-4-nitrobenzene by an amino group renders the hydrolysis of the CN group extremely difficult. The Cl atom, moreover, cannot be knocked off from the nucleus by means of caustic potash.

Several interesting derivatives of 2-chloro-5-nitrobenzoic acid have been prepared, incidentally, during the study of the reactivity of the chlorine atom in this compound. These derivatives have been made through the acid chloride, the latter being most conveniently obtained by the action of thionyl chloride on the acid: this method

gives a far better yield than that of Montagne (*Rec. trav. Chim.*, 1900, **19**, 57). The several amides were made by shaking an aqueous suspension of the acid chloride with various amines, *e.g.*, ethyl amine (III), propylamine (IV), diethylamine (V), ethylenediamine (VI), etc., while the ureide (VII) was obtained by fusing the chloride with urea.

(III)

(IV)

(V)

(VI)

(VII)

These amides were prepared in the hope that the reactive chlorine atom might be made to interact with a hydrogen atom of the alkyl group, leading to the closure of an *isoquinoline* ring thus :

Repeated attempts made in this direction, however, using such agents as copper dust, AlCl_3 , PbO , POCl_3 , etc., failed to give the desired result. The amides were found to be extremely stable, the ethylamide, for example, being recovered unchanged even after vigorous boiling with PCl_5 and POCl_3 for several hours.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Hydrolysis of the Chloro-, Ethoxy- and Methoxynitrobenzonnitriles.

A. 1-Chloro-2-cyano-4-nitrobenzene. *Hydrolysis with H₂SO₄: 2-Chloro-5-nitrobenzamide.*—Chlorocyanonitrobenzene (2 g.), moistened with 10-12 drops of water, was slowly treated with conc. sulphuric acid (10 c.c.). The slightly coloured, clear warm liquid was heated over a free flame to simmer for about 10 minutes until it just began to fume, and poured after half an hour into cold water (50 c.c.). The precipitate crystallised from boiling water (with the addition of a few c.c. alcohol) in shining white needles, m.p. 178°, yield about 2 g. This product had been obtained by Montagne (*loc. cit.*) by the action of aqueous ammonia on 2-chloro-5-nitrobenzoyl chloride.

On boiling with 10% caustic potash, the *amide* went into a clear yellow solution, with the evolution of ammonia and the formation of 5-nitrosalicylic acid (m.p. 228°).

Hydrolysis of the amide with HCl: 2-Chloro-5-nitrobenzoic acid.—Chloronitrobenzamide (2 g.) was boiled with conc. HCl (10-12 c.c.) on a wire gauze for an hour. On cooling, the product separated from the clear liquid and was purified by recrystallisation from boiling water, (m. p. 164°). On boiling this acid with 10% potash 5-nitrosalicylic acid was obtained.

B. 1-Ethoxy-2-cyano-4-nitrobenzene.

Hydrolysis with H₂SO₄: 2-Ethoxy-5-nitrobenzamide.—1-Ethoxy-2-cyano-4-nitrobenzene was hydrolysed with H₂SO₄ just as in the previous case. The product crystallised from dilute alcohol in small white needles, m.p. 176°. (Found: N, 13.51. C₉H₁₀O₄N₂ requires N, 13.34 per cent).

2-Ethoxy-5-nitrobenzoic acid was prepared by boiling 2-ethoxy-5-nitrobenzamide with concentrated HCl for 1 hour as in the previous case and crystallised from dilute alcohol in almost white needles, m.p. 162°. (Found: N, 6.71. Calc.: N, 6.63 per cent).

Boiling with potash converted both the *amide* and the *acid* into 5-nitrosalicylic acid (m.p. 228°).

C. 1-Methoxy-2-cyano-4-nitrobenzene.

Hydrolysis with H₂SO₄: 2-Methoxy-5-nitrobenzamide (II), obtained just as in the case of the ethoxy analogue by sulphuric acid hydrolysis of the corresponding nitrile, melted at 212°. (Found: N, 14.13. C₈H₈O₄N requires N, 14.33 per cent).

2-Methoxy-5-nitrobenzoic acid was similarly obtained by boiling 2-methoxy-5-nitrobenzamide with concentrated HCl for 1 hour, m. p. 151°. (Found: N, 7.28. Calc.: N, 7.11 per cent).

Boiling with caustic potash converted both the amide and the acid into 5-nitrosalicylic acid (m. p. 228°).

Derivatives of 2-Chloro-5-nitrobenzoic Acid.

2-Chloro-5-nitrobenzoyl chloride.—Chloronitrobenzoic acid (30 g.), mixed with excess of thionyl chloride (40 g.), was heated on a water-bath in the usual way until no more HCl fumes were given off. The clear liquid was now distilled from the water-bath under reduced pressure, when it solidified to a crystalline mass. The last traces of thionyl chloride were removed by washing with ice-water and the product dried on a plate in a vacuum desiccator. Colourless cube-shaped crystals, m.p. 59°, yield 28 g. This substance had been obtained in a much poorer yield by Montagne (*loc. cit.*) by the action of PCl₅ on chloronitrobenzoic acid.

2-Chloro-5-nitrobenzamide (*cf.* Montagne, *loc. cit.*).—On shaking a suspension of the chloride in water with aqueous ammonia, the amide was formed crystallising from water in white needles, m.p. 176°, identical with the product obtained by the hydrolysis of chloro-2-cyano-4-nitrobenzene with H₂SO₄.

The *methylamide* (*cf.* Montagne, *loc. cit.*) was obtained by similarly shaking a suspension of the chloride in water with methylamine (33% aqueous or alcoholic solution), m.p. 171°.

The *ethylamide*.—The chloride (2 g.), finely suspended in water (10 c.c.), was slowly treated in the cold with ethylamine (88%, 5 c.c.), the mixture shaken for 1 hour and the cream-coloured precipitate crystallised from boiling water with the addition of a little alcohol as glistening white flakes, m.p. 148°, yield 1.7 g. (Found: N, 12.35. C₉H₉O₃N₂Cl requires N, 12.25 per cent).

The *propylamide*, prepared from the chloride and propylamine, crystallised from boiling water in shining flakes, m.p. 142°. (Found: N, 11.73. C₁₀H₁₁O₃N₂Cl requires N, 11.55 per cent).

The *2-diethylamide*, prepared by the action of diethylamine on the chloride, crystallised from alcohol in pale yellow needles, m.p. 72°. (Found: N, 11.19. $C_{11}H_{13}O_3N_2Cl$ requires N, 10.29 per cent).

The *ethylenediamide* was obtained as a white amorphous powder from the chloride and ethylenediamine. It could not be crystallised from any suitable solvent and was purified by washing with hot acetic acid, m.p. 310°. (Found: N, 13.29. $C_{16}H_{12}O_6N_4Cl_2$ requires N, 13.11 per cent).

The *ureide*.—The chloride (2 g.) and urea (1.5 g.) were warmed together on the free flame when the mixture melted and reacted vigorously with the evolution of NH_4Cl fumes. Carbon tetrachloride (10 c.c.) was added and the paste thoroughly mixed and heated again (5-10 minutes). The product was filtered, washed with methanol and crystallised from acetic acid as clusters of hard, perfectly white needles, m.p. 216°. (Found: N, 17.53. $C_8H_6O_4N_3Cl$ requires N, 17.25 per cent).

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